

MEDICAL SCIENCES

BREAST CANCER, RISK FACTORS AND THE EFFECT OF EARLY SCREENING IN WOMEN LIFE. A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Every year, in worldwide many women diagnosed, treated and died by breast cancer. Coping with this pathology is a big challenge not only for patients but also their families too. This is a descriptive and retrospective study which aims to evaluate the frequency of breast cancer in Kurbin, Albania as well as the assessment of preventive measures from. For data analysis is used the statistical package 20.0 and data are expressed in frequency and percentage. It was considered significant the p value <0.05. From 2016 to 2019 are screened 592 women of which 72 cases are diagnosed with breast cancer. The screening is more frequent in urban area than in rural area. The age over 50 years old is a high risk factor for this pathology. The year with the highest incidence of breast cancer is 2016 with 36 cases (46.2 %) followed by 2019 with 21 (27%) cases. Laçi is the town with the highest incidence of breast cancer. It is noticed that with the increasing of screening the mortality decrease. There is a statistically significant difference between women with different level education, which mean that women with high education level reflect low cases of breast cancer compare of them with 8-year education level which are 47% of all cases.

Keywords: breast cancer, cancer's symptoms, mammography, treatment, palliative care, breast examination.

Background

Breast cancer is a common frequent disease for women and threat their lives too. Worldwide, the breast cancer has a mediatic and political profile. The month of October is the month dedicated this pathology where all the health care providers emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and treatment. Many studies are dedicated to this pathology and the pink ribbon is its symbol in order to attract the attention of women as much as possible to sensitize them[1].

Breast cancer is a cancer that metastasizes at a distance such as in: bones, liver, lungs, brain. Self examination, physical examination, mammography but also MRI are screening procedures which help in early diagnosis of breast cancer and help reduce the mortality as well [2-4]. The risk factors that enhance the possibility to have breast cancer are: age, family history, early menarche, late menopause, life style, female hormone[5-9].

Breast cancer is associated with much concerns even for those women that have good progress and successful treatment for this disease. These women experience emotional, social and physical challenges. Physical concerns, poor quality of sleeping, body damage, social isolation, interruption of daily activity that interfere in the quality of life[10-13]. The more aggressive the cancer is, the symptoms are noticed fast, but also it spread faster and the prognosis is poor. The slower the cancer grows, more difficult it is to observe the symptoms early, delaying the diagnosis and consequently the treatment [14-16].

All midwives who take care for these women diagnosed with breast cancer reflect increase professional skills over time. The goal and need of midwives to continuously grow professionally is precisely to be as supportive as possible for the woman but also for her family members [17]. Their contribution is in early screening of this cancer, the health care before, during and after surgical treatment, taking care during radiotherapy and also the follow up. Midwives must use advanced knowledge to determine the health needs or even preferences for these women with breast cancer to maintain health and well-being at various stage. This is achieved through the continuum of taking care including diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation and palliative care [18-20]. **The aim** of this study is to evaluate the cases of breast cancer in Kurbin and the assessment of women's knowledge and preventive measures.

Methods

Design

This is a retrospective and descriptive study.

Sample

It is conducted in Kurbin District in Albania. This district consist of: Fushe-Kuqe, Laç, Mamurras, Milot. It has an area of 235 km² and it population si about 740000 residents.

Data collection

The obtained data was collected by the clinical charts from the statistics department at primary health care. In this study are involved all clinical charts from 2016 to 2019.

Data evaluation included demographic data such as: birth place, living place, woman's education, examinations and also risk factors. The variables are expressed in frequency and percentage and it is used for statistical analysis the statistical package version of SPSS 20.0. It is considered as statistically significant the p-value <0.05.

Results

This survey is conducted in Kurbin District in Albania from 2016 to 2019 and the age of the participant range between 25- + 65 years old. According to the clinical charts of years from 2016 to 2019 results that

there are 592 women who were screening for breast cancer. As we see the screening rate increases year after year. It culminates at 2019 with 90 screening for the group age 45-54 years old. The lowest incidence was in 2017 with only 2 screening for the group age + 65 years old. The age group with the highest screening for breast cancer is 45-54 years old with 274 (46.3%) women and the lowest belong to the group age of 25-34 years old with 26 (4.4%) women. At 2019 we see a greater awareness of women for screening tests who were more interested for breast echo.

Table 1

Year	Total	Age				
		25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	+65
2016	86	5	3	41	34	3
2017	109	3	6	54	44	2
2018	195	7	14	89	73	12
2019	202	11	9	90	82	10

Among 592 screening test results that there are 78 cases diagnosed with breast cancer. The table 2 shows us the distribution of cases according the years and living place. The year with the highest incidence of breast cancer results in 2016 with 36 (46.2 %) cases out of 78 in total. Laçi has the largest number of women with

breast cancer and this is also due to the fact that it has the highest number of people who live in this town more than in other areas. And there are 41(53%) cases with breast cancer. While the lowest cases are in Milot with 9 cases. 64% of diagnostic women live in urban area and 36% of them in rural area.

Table 2

Living place	Years			
	2016	2017	2018	2019
Laç	19	5	7	10
F-Kuçe	0	1	2	3
Mamurras	12	3	1	6
Milot	5	2	0	2

According to the data collected in clinical charts results that risk factors that predominate most are as they are showed in the table below.

Table 3

Risk factors	Case number (78 in total)	Frequency %
Age \geq 50	44	56%
Stress	24	31%
Nulliparity	7	9%
alcohol consumption	0	0%
Smoking	3	4%

The age is the predominant risk factor in 78 women diagnosed with breast cancer. A significant relationship was found between this two variables with a p-value = 0.02.

In this survey 8 (11%) women with university level education have experience breast cancer and 37 (47%) out of 78 cases with breast cancer belongs to women with elementary level education. This table shows for a correlation between women's level education and frequency of breast cancer.

Table 4

Women's level education	Case number	Frequency %
Elementary	37	47%
High	33	42%
University	8	11%

Table 5

Screening	Breast cancer screening	
	Case number (78)	Frequency %
Breast self-examination	23	30
Mammography	33	42
Echo	19	24
Biopsy	3	4

As we see from the table above, we realize that in this survey the screening test that diagnostic most is mammography. 33 (42%) out of 78 women are diagnostic by this screening test. 23 of them are diagnostic by self-examination and only 3 of women are diagnostic by biopsy.

The classification of breast cancer according the type of carcinoma. In this population or women who are diagnosed with breast cancer 64 (82%) of them are diagnosed with ductal carcinoma in situ which means that the cancer is not spread in healthy tissue and 18% out of 78 women are diagnosed with invasive ductal carcinoma.

Graphic 1

Discussion

From the databases and various studies, it has been estimated that every year about 1.500.000 new cases of breast cancer are experienced worldwide. 60% of them experience in developing countries. It is considered a good prognosis when the survival is about 73 % in developed countries while in developing countries age 53 % [21-22].

According to our study results that from 592 screening test 78 women are diagnosed with breast cancer. The most affected age were 50 years old women with 56 % of cases. Also, the other worldwide studies have the same find about age which means that the highest risk for breast cancer is about this age while with the increasing age the risk of breast cancer decreases [23-24]. We realize that, year after year for all that places that are included for study there is an increasing trend of screening tests for breast cancer realizing that women have begun to be aware of their health and early diagnosis significantly reduces mortality[25].

The year with the highest incidence for this diagnose was 2016 with 46.2%, where the same year had the lowest screening tests compared to other years. The place with the highest number of cases was Laçi and this is due to highest population.

Level education is another risk factor for breast cancer. In our study level education represent a statistically significant deference between women with different level education. We have only 8 women with university level education who are diagnosed with breast

cancer. Thus, the level education and socio-economic condition are significant factors in screening and treatment of this diagnose[26-28]. According to the screening tests, in our survey results that mammography takes the first place for breast cancer diagnosis followed by breast self-examination. Mammography is a successful screening test helping to reduce the mortality. It helps in early detection [29-30].

Conclusion

Breast cancer is a worldwide concern and increasing too. It is fatal if it isn't diagnosed early. Screening programs like as mammography, breast self-examination, echo and adequate information help women live longer and experience a quality life.

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